

Table S1. Clinical outcomes in the pre-treatment and post-treatment samples after empagliflozin or metformin intervention

	Empagliflozin (n = 40)			Metformin (n = 36)			P-value Pre-treatment (Empagliflozin vs. Metformin)	P-value Post-treatment (Empagliflozin vs. Metformin)
	Pre-treatment	Post-treatment	P-value	Pre-treatment	Post-treatment	P-value		
Age (years)	47.7±10.8	-	-	45.5±8.9	-	-	0.300	-
Male [n/(%)]	26 (65)	-	-	26 (72)	-	-	0.499	-
Anthropometric measurements								
Body weight (kg)	78.1±16.1	74.7±16.6	<0.0001	77.7±8.3	75.8±8.8	0.025	0.463	0.246
BMI (kg/m ²)	27.9±4.2	26.5±4.3	<0.0001	27.8±3.6	26.9±3.0	0.006	0.884	0.410
WC (cm)	95.4±11.1	90.5±10.5	<0.0001	95.8±7.8	91.8±6.5	<0.0001	0.755	0.252
WHR	0.96±0.05	0.93±0.04	<0.0001	0.97±0.04	0.95±0.04	0.002	0.486	0.172
Glucose-related measurements								
HbA1c (%)	8.9±1.9	6.7±0.7	<0.0001	9.2±1.7	6.5±0.7	<0.0001	0.365	0.332
FPG (mmol/L)	7.4±1.5	7.0±1.2	0.082	6.9±1.4	6.7±1.4	0.347	0.181	0.236
PPG (mmol/L)	16.5±2.5	12.5±3.3	<0.0001	15.6±2.4	12.9±3.0	<0.0001	0.171	0.920
AUC blood glucose (mmol/L*min)	2646±440	2066±440	<0.0001	2499±319	2162±310	0.001	0.374	0.765
AUC insulin (pmol/L*min)	5322±3546	4424±2827	0.128	4570±5741	4130±3651	0.431	0.063	0.193
HOMA-IR	3.42±2.06	2.00±1.58	0.014	2.09±1.45	1.71±1.17	0.011	0.004	0.550
β-hydroxybutyrate (mmol/L)	0.13±0.11	0.24±0.36	0.204	0.09±0.08	0.07±0.05	0.602	0.154	0.002
Blood pressure-related measurements								
SBP (mmHg)	130.7±14.8	121.7±10.2	0.0002	128.7±13.9	126.3±10.3	0.331	0.441	0.155
DBP (mmHg)	79.8±9.8	75.2±8.2	0.005	79.3±10.0	78.0±10.1	0.559	0.979	0.263
Blood lipid-related measurements								
TG (mmol/L)	2.8±1.6	2.2±1.1	0.011	2.3±1.5	2.1±1.1	0.511	0.115	0.616
TC (mmol/L)	5.0±0.9	4.7±0.9	0.062	4.7±0.7	4.4±0.7	0.212	0.119	0.170

LDL-C (mmol/L)	2.7±0.8	2.7±0.8	0.704	2.4±0.7	2.5±0.6	0.986	0.151	0.300
HDL-C (mmol/L)	1.1±0.2	1.2±0.3	0.310	1.0±0.2	1.1±0.2	0.031	0.718	0.885
Free fatty acid (mmol/L)	0.56±0.20	0.71±0.28	0.018	0.46±0.19	0.54±0.22	0.054	0.027	0.007
Adiponectin (mg/L)	2.8±1.3	3.6±1.4	<0.0001	3.1±1.3	3.1±1.3	0.415	0.362	0.184
Fatty liver related measurements								
ALT (U/L)	34.4±19.8	24.2±10.9	0.006	30.1±16.8	27.6±13.7	0.165	0.392	0.363
AST (U/L)	25.5±9.8	22.1±6.4	0.181	22.4±9.1	21.1±5.8	0.304	0.128	0.697
GGT (U/L)	43.7±25.0	33.0±24.8	<0.0001	32.7±16.8	23.8±9.1	0.0001	0.030	0.205
HSI	41.1±6.8	37.8±5.4	<0.0001	40.7±6.0	39.8±4.7	0.120	0.978	0.069
FIB-4	0.18±0.09	0.21±0.10	0.097	0.19±0.13	0.17±0.07	0.859	0.830	0.099
Renal function-related measurements								
UA (µmol/L)	356.0±101.6	303.1±98.1	0.001	318.6±70.8	337.1±70.4	0.392	0.062	0.478
Creatine (µmol/L)	55.8±13.6	56.6±11.0	0.765	56.3±11.0	54.4±9.8	0.564	0.774	0.463
A/C (mg/g)	28.8±39.0	27.1±47.3	0.202	22.3±36.7	24.8±36.7	0.577	0.104	0.296
eGFR (mL/min/1.73 m ²)	176.5±40.3	170.5±33.4	0.543	177.7±35.9	182.7±28.7	0.634	0.774	0.062
Inflammatory factors								
LBP (ng/mL)	5.4±3.9	6.1±3.6	0.307	11.6±3.8	11.6±3.7	0.899	<0.0001	<0.0001
IL-6 (pg/mL)	9.1±8.7	6.0±8.8	0.0001	5.3±1.6	4.5±1.4	0.023	0.020	0.874
TNF-α (pg/mL)	1.3±0.9	0.6±0.6	0.0004	1.7±0.8	1.1±0.4	0.0003	0.041	<0.0001
Number of risk factors for CVD [n/(%)]							0.274	0.364
0	0 (0)	1 (3)	1.000	0 (0)	2 (6)	0.500		
1	7 (18)	14 (38)	0.039	12 (33)	10 (31)	0.774		
2 and more	33 (82)	22 (59)	0.008	24 (67)	20 (62)	1.000		
Medicine use								
Statin treatment n (%)	15 (38)	-	-	18 (50)	-	-	0.272	-
Antihypertensive treatment n (%)	11 (28)	-	-	8 (22)	-	-	0.596	-

Risk factors for CVD included a) SBP $\geq$ 140 mmHg or DBP $\geq$ 90 mmHg; b) being older than 50 years for male or 60 years for female; c) LDL-C $\geq$ 2.6 mmol/L or TG $\geq$ 2.3 mmol/L or HDL-C $\leq$ 0.88 mmol/L; d) BMI $\geq$ 28 kg/m²; e) urine ACR $\geq$ 30; f) ABI of either side $\leq$ 0.9.

BMI, body mass index; WC, waist circumference; WHR, waist–hip circumference ratio; HbA1c, glycated hemoglobin; FPG, fasting plasma glucose; PPG, postprandial plasma glucose; AUC, area under the curve; HOMA-IR, homeostasis model assessment of insulin resistance; HCT, hematocrit; SBP, systolic blood pressure; DBP, diastolic blood pressure; TG, total triglycerides; TC, total cholesterol; LDL-C, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol; HDL-C, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; AST, aspartate aminotransferase; ALP, alkaline phosphatase; GGT, γ -glutamyl transpeptidase; HIS, hepatic steatosis index; FIB-4, FIB-4 index; UA, uric acid; A/C, urine albumin creatinine ratio; eGFR, estimated glomerular filtration rate; LBP, lipopolysaccharide-binding protein; IL-6, interleukin-6; and TNF- α , tumor necrosis factor α .

Data are presented as the mean $\pm$ SD.

Figure S1. Flowchart of the study

Figure S2. Orthogonal projection to latent structure-discriminant analysis (OPLS-DA) score plots of plasma metabolites

- A) Comparisons under the negative ionic mode for the empagliflozin group.
- B) Comparisons under the negative ionic mode for the metformin group.
- C) Comparisons under the positive ionic mode for the empagliflozin group.
- D) Comparisons under the positive ionic mode for the metformin group.

Figure S3. Changes in the α -diversity of the gut microbiota at 0 w, 4 w, 8 w, and 12 w in patients treated with empagliflozin or metformin

A) Observed ASVs of the gut microbiota at 0 w, 4 w, 8 w, and 12 w in patients treated with empagliflozin.

B) Observed ASVs of the gut microbiota at 0 w, 4 w, 8 w, and 12 w in patients treated with metformin.

C) Shannon index of the gut microbiota at 0 w, 4 w, 8 w, and 12 w in patients treated with empagliflozin.

D) Shannon index of the gut microbiota at 0 w, 4 w, 8 w, and 12 w in patients treated with metformin.

All data are shown as the average $\pm$ SEM; the observed ASVs and Shannon indexes at 4 w, 8 w, and 12 w were compared with those at 0 w in each group using Mix effects analysis with Dunnett's multiple tests. * P -value < 0.05; ** P -value < 0.01.

Figure S4. ASVs contributing to the changes in the gut microbiota in patients treated with empagliflozin or metformin

- A) ASVs contributing to the changes in the gut microbiota in the empagliflozin group at 0 w and 4 w.
 - B) ASVs contributing to the changes in the gut microbiota in the empagliflozin group at 0 w and 8 w.
 - C) ASVs contributing to the changes in the gut microbiota in the empagliflozin group at 0 w and 12 w.
 - D) ASVs contributing to the changes in the gut microbiota in the metformin group at 0 w and 4 w.
 - E) ASVs contributing to the changes in the gut microbiota in the metformin group at 0 w and 8 w.
 - F) ASVs contributing to the changes in the gut microbiota in the metformin group at 0 w and 12 w.
- All the differential ASVs were identified using the LEfSe model.